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Application of Landsat Imagery for Land Cover Analysis of MBE Mountain and Wildlife Sanctuary in Cross River State Nigeria

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Abstract

This study examined the integration of remote sensing (RS) and Geographic Information System (GIS) tool to forest resource mapping and monitoring in Mbe Mountain Forest and Wildlife Sanctuary. Landsat satellite imageries for 1987, 2001, 2013 and 2019 covering 32 year period were used to classify and identify forest changes through change detection techniques. The result showed a general conversion from forested areas to degraded landscape in all the years under review except in 2019 Result showed that degraded areas were derived not only from previously forested zones but also from areas previously occupied by water bodies and rocky outcrops. Deliberate re-channeling of water courses within the reserve to aid irrigation purposes to farms outside the protected area was a causal factor in the conversion of areas previously occupied by water bodies while artisanal mining activities had leveled rocky outcrops to bare grounds. It was observed that degradation rate was discriminatory as it was highest in the southern and eastern flank of the reserve bordering Okwango Division of the Cross River National Park (CRNP). The responsible for this are late establishment of Ecoguards and partial enforcement of regulatory laws. Over all, the reluctance of Federal government to officially gazette the reserve as a protected area on its own or its fusion into the Okwango Division of the CRNP was observed as the main deforestation trigger. Furthermore, the continuous decline in forest cover is predicted for 2025 with a corresponding 19.8 % conversion of forest landscape into degraded lands. This may result in total loss of forest cover around Bamba, Abo Mkpang, Abo Obisu and Wula areas leaving Kanyang 1 and 11 only as zones occupied by forests. The findings of this research is to be shared with Wildlife Conservation Society, the nine host communities and the Ministry of Biodiversity and Climate Change Forestry Commission with a view to influencing decisions making that would halt the deforestation rate.

Key words: LandSat, Imagery, Wildlife, Sanctuary, Ecoguards, Deforestation.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

A major consequence of the quest for socio- economic development especially in Third World Countries is pressure on the available forest resources. This has continually established a dynamic change in land use pattern. Most pristine forests have long been modified into agricultural fields (Beatrice *et al.*, 2019), industrial estates (Levis *et al.*, 2018), infrastructural hubs (Levis *et al.*, 2018) and residential concerns (Nahari, 2018). These developments have mushroomed into grave impacts on ecosystem integrity and functioning. Species loss and habitat fragmentation, loss of important flora and fauna species and loss of threatened livelihood sources are few of the direct effects of modified land scape. There is also a weighty indirect consequence of the direct impacts. Climate change and its twin evil, global warming. The world has been getting warmer as global average temperature for the first 10 months of 2018 was 0.98⁰C above the levels of 1850-1900. The 20 warmest years on record have been in the past 22 years, with 2015-2018 making up the top four (WMO 2019). If this trend continues, temperatures may rise by 3-5⁰C by 2100 (WMO 2019). The impact of this data on human

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existence is grave. Sea levels will rise, ocean temperatures and acidity will increase and our ability to grow crops, such as rice, maize and wheat which constitute about 80% of human food source would be impaired (McClare *et al.*, 2018). Large parts of the northern hemisphere where Nigeria and Africa belong shall continuously see a succession of heat waves as a result of strong high pressure systems that has created a "heat dome" (Armstrong *et al.*, 2019). About 95% of cities facing extreme climate risks are in Africa and Asia, as faster-growing cities including megacities like Lagos and Kinshasa in the Democratic Republic of Congo would be severely impacted by extreme risks from rising temperatures and extreme weather brought on by climate change (Hunt *et al.*, 2018). The role deforestation plays in the above mentioned impacts is better evaluated when one considers that beef cattle raised on deforested land produces 12 times more greenhouse gas emissions than those reared on natural pastures (WMO 2019).

Mapping of available forest resources depicting areas of sustained and renewed anthropogenic and natural pressures have helped shaped climate change policies. Forest are excellent sinks for carbon sequestration (Zhu *et al.*, 2018). In Nigeria as in most African Countries, application of land cover analyses using satellite imagery to geo-spatially map forest capitals have been largely isolated and driven by private enterprise for mostly private consumption. The few available land cover analyses were either conducted prior to 2000 (Warren *et al.*, 2004). The few conducted after the turn of the Millennium were conducted to map the forest at resolutions of not less than 30m. The implications are that very fine and minute details could not be unraveled.

With Cross River State being home to World recognized biodiversity conservation hot spots such as the Cross River National Park, Afi Mountain and Wildlife Sanctuary and host of communally and state administered forest reserves, mapping of the available vegetal land cover is all the most impelling. Regrettably, these forests are yet to be digitally mapped. Mbe Mountain Wildlife Sanctuary, a communally owned reserve, situated on a high altitudinal plateau and home to the endemic *Gorilla gorilladehli* was mapped to a 30m resolution height by Imong *et al* (2014).

Applications of land cover analyses has become even more compelling in today's world occasioned principally by modifications of land use systems through natural and anthropogenic pressures. Land use –Land cover analyses referring to the categorization of human activities and natural elements on the landscape within a specified time frame based on established scientific and statistical methods of referenced source has found wide applicability in change detection analyses (Chang *et al* 2018). In developed countries, land use-land cover (LULC) maps play pivotal role in planning, management, and monitoring programs at all levels of spatial gradients (Mukete *et al* 2017) For instance, the employment of LULC maps by Mannan *et al* (2019) helped monitored and project forest carbon biomass loss while Juliev *et al* (2018) applied it for the categorization of forest resources. Batar (2017) applied LULC maps in forests into various land use systems.

In Nigeria as in other third world countries with huge pressures on forest resources, emphasis on the limited studies is concentrated on change analyses within urban settlement (Olujide *et al* 2018, Olurunfemi *et al* 2018, Atubiet *al* 2018, Iwuji *et al* 2017 and Babalola *et al* 2014). A careful analyses of these reports revealed a biased on pressures fuelled by infrastructural developments due to rural-urban migration. On review, the authors were largely social scientists. These studies are best described as reactionary to products of pressures and not proactive as done in developed climes. Proactive studies done in pristine forests published as reports in Nigeria is scanty. Imong *et al* (2014) represent one of the extremely few done for planning and monitoring in a forest not just in Nigeria but in Mbe and Afi, Cross River State. As potent and useful as this study is, the imagery power of 30 m would have obscured the finest land cover spectral and signatures that one of 10m or below would have revealed. More so, within the intervening six years period between Imong studies and the present research, changes in land use and land cover in the forest is predicted. This study is even all the more needed since Imong *et al* (2014) concentrated on fauna wildlife and not on flora wildlife, which is the nous of this research. It is based on these challenges that the current study is justified. The primary aim of this research is

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the application of landsat imagery in establishing a geospatial mapping of the Mbe Mountain and Wildlife Sanctuary. The objectives are: to map out the different land cover habitats and their spatial distribution; to delineate the boundaries of the Mbe Mountain and Wildlife Sanctuary; to identify, quantify and map out the changes in Mbe mountain using landsat imageries; to examine the specific human activities types responsible for the changes and to model/ predict possible future changes

2.0 MATERIALS AND METHOD

2.1 Study area

The Mbe mountain and wild life sanctuary is located in the Boki Local Government Area of Cross Rivers State Nigeria. It lies between latitude $06^{\circ} 14' 17''$ and $06^{\circ} 20' 46''$ latitude and $09^{\circ} 14' 12''$ and $09^{\circ} 8' 23''$ East which covers an area approximately 22 square kilometers as shown in Fig. 1.

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Fig.1: Location of the Study Area.

2.2 Analysis of Historic Deforestation

Remote sensing data used for this analysis usually should fulfill certain quality requirements regarding resolution. Medium resolution data such as Landsat (30 x 30 m pixels) is sufficient. In order to allow credible

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projections, remote sensing data for a minimum of three time periods inclusive of historic reference periods was used.

2.3 Acquisition and Processing of Image Data sets

Traditional land cover change analysis techniques use aerial photographs and satellite images taken at multiple times to assess the amount of land cover change between two or more time periods (Lilles and Kiefer, 1994). These techniques depend on accurate land cover classifications of the remotely sensed images to compare land cover changes over time. Algorithms for conducting land cover change analysis include the traditional and widely used post classification comparison (Lu *et al.*, 2007; Sader *et al.*, 2001; Yuan *et al.*, 2005; Kozak *et al.*, 2007; Coppin *et al.*, 2004), composite analysis (Coppin *et al.*, 2004; Singh, 1989; Pilon *et al.*, 1988), univariate image differencing (Coppin *et al.*, 2004), and others. See Coppin *et al.*, 2004 for a review of land change algorithms.

2.4 Image Pre-processing

The Landsat imagery used for this study was acquired from the US Geological Survey GLOVIS webbased data service (glovis.usgs.gov), in L1T (level 1 Terrain-corrected) format. This is an ortho-rectified product that generally has sufficient spatial accuracy to allow direct comparison between images. Also radiometric correction was carried out to ensure that reflectance values between different Landsat scenes could be compared. These images were identified as Landsat path 187, row 56 and cover the entire study area. For the early dates, 1987 and 2001, Landsat 5 TM images were used. For the 2013 and 2019 dates, two Landsat 7 ETM+ images were obtained, one as it is necessary to use two images in order to eliminate the striping due to the scan line correction failure in the Landsat 7 satellite

Table 1: Remotely sensed image datasets used for the deforestation study.

Satellite	Sensor	Resolution		Coverage(km2)	Acquisition Date(dd/mm/yyyy)	Scene Identifier	
		Spatial	Spectral			Path	Row
Landasta-5	TM	30 x 30m	6 bands	10.8 x 11.2	12_12_1987	187	56
Landasta-7	ETM+	30 x 30m	6 bands	10.8 x 11.2	10_12_2011	187	56
Landasta-7	ETM+	30 x 30m	6 bands	Landasta-5	01_01_2013	187	56
Landasta-7	ETM+	30 x 30m	6 bands	Landasta-5	04_01_2019	187	56

This study used the post classification comparison method, where multiple dates of satellite images were first classified into land cover images and then compared to assess changes in land cover over time. To prepare the images for classification, spectral enhancement was performed on the rectified image. Spectral enhancements are modifications of the pixel values of an image. They can be used to improve interpretability, reduce information redundancy, and extract information from the data which is not readily visible in its raw form. The two enhancements utilized for this study were principal components analysis and the tasseled cap transformation.

2.5 Statistical Analyses for Image Classification

The image classification for this study was carried out using maximum likelihood classifier. Image classification generally involves labeling the pixels as belonging to particular spectral class using the spectral

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data available. It was assumed in this study that the spectral classes for an image be represented by ω_i and the pixel as x . To determine the class or category to which a pixel x belongs, it was strictly the conditional probabilities $p(\omega_i|x)$. (Makinde *et al*, 2001). This is the probability that the class (ω_i) is the correct for a pixel at position x where

$$i = 1 \dots m$$

m =total number of classes.

The image classification was performed according to

$x \in \omega_i$, if

$$p(\omega_i|x) > p(\omega_j|x) \text{ for all } j \neq i$$

This means that the pixel at position x belongs to class ω_i if $p(\omega_i|x)$ is the largest. One major problem that associates with this classifier is that $p(\omega_i|x)$ are not always known. To estimate a probability distribution for a land cover type (i.e. a class) that describes the chance of finding a pixel from class ω_i at position x (i.e. $p(x|\omega_i)$), this study ensured that sufficient training samples were available as recommended by (John *et al*, 2006). They recommend as a practical minimum that $10N$ training pixels per spectral class be used, where N is the number of channels. The dimensionality of data (images) that was used in this research is low (3-channel multispectral images), therefore achieving these numbers was not impossible.

2.6 Map Projection

The CA-Markov analysis was run to test a pair of land cover images and outputs a transition probability matrix and a transition area matrix. To project, the study used cellular automata markov change prediction module in Idrisi software (Agbor *et al*, 2012). This was also manually calculated using matrix model (equation 9). Both methods utilized the transition probability matrix generated from image cross classification

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} x_{a_{11}} & x_{a_{12}} & x_{a_{13}} \\ x_{a_{22}} & x_{a_{22}} & x_{a_{23}} \\ x_{a_{31}} & x_{a_{32}} & x_{a_{33}} \end{pmatrix} B = \begin{pmatrix} x_{b_1} \\ x_{b_2} \\ x_{b_3} \end{pmatrix} C = \begin{pmatrix} x_{c_1} \\ x_{c_2} \\ x_{c_3} \end{pmatrix}$$

Where

A = Array of probability values of land cover types conversion for the three classes.

B = Percentage of land cover types for the base year.

C = Projected matrix

The product of A and B matrices produced the forecast values matrix C for each land cover type.

The transition probability matrix explains the probability that each land cover category changed to every other category. The transition areas matrix is the number of pixels that are expected to change from each land cover type to every other land cover type over the specified number of time unit e.g. 6years in this study.

2.7 Image Detection

The changes were determined by subtracting the value of a land cover type of the earlier year from the more recent year.

2.8 Mapping of land cover and land cover change

Once processed, unsupervised classification method was used to obtain land cover type. This method assigns pixels to one of 60 unique clusters based on the spectral response of the pixel across all spectral bands, using the ISODATA unsupervised classification technique (ERDAS, 2010; Jensen, 1996). Next, each pixel cluster was assessed to determine the predominant land cover type of the pixels within the cluster. The assignment of a predominant land cover type was based on a visual inspection of the location and appearance of the pixels and ancillary data, including 2010 field data from WCS. If an original cluster contained a mix of

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more than one land cover class, it was set aside for further processing. This processing involved running the ISODATA algorithm on the mixed cluster to further break it apart into ten new clusters. These ten clusters were again visually inspected, class trajectories identified and incorporated back into the original scene. This process led to seven land cover classifications, one each for 1987 and 2001 and two for the 2013/2019 images. Because of the failure of the scan line corrector on Landsat 7, all post-2003 satellite images suffer from no data banding or gaps at the edges of the scene.

Therefore, the two separate images were classified and used the 2013 land cover to fill in the gaps in the 2019 land cover resulting on one final cover scene representing the most current land cover in the landscape. Next, the multiple land cover types in each scene were re-classed into five land cover types: forest, grassland/low vegetation, human settlements/bare earth/rock/burned grass, disturbed forest/farmland and water. This was done because of the need to focus mostly on transitions from forest to any other land cover type in order to better model deforestation in the future and to ensure a higher overall classification accuracy.

Fig.2: Satellite images from 1987, 2001, and 2013 used for historic deforestation analysis.

2.9 Accuracy assessment

An accuracy assessment was performed to determine the quality of the land cover analysis. With limited historical data on true land cover types, an independent sample of an average of 112 polygons, with about 90 pixels for each selected polygon, was randomly selected from each classification to assess classification accuracies. Error matrices as cross-tabulations of the mapped class vs. the reference class were used to assess classification accuracy (Congalton & Green, 1999). Overall accuracy, user's and producer's accuracies, and the Kappa statistic were then derived from the error matrices. The results indicated that classification process provided average of overall accuracy and Kappa values of 94.1% and 0.93, respectively for 1987, 2001, 2013 and 2019 (Table 2). This result is slightly above the minimum mapping accuracy of 90% required by most VCS AFOLU methodologies.

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Table 2: Summary of landsat classification accuracies (%) for 1987, 2001, 2013 and 2019.

Land Cover Class	1987		2001		2013		2019	
	Producer	User	Producer	User	Producer	User	Producer	User
Forest	92.5	92.7	92.9	92.7	93.3	92.7	93.3	93.4
Non forest	93.7	94.1	93.8	94.1	93.1	93.8	93.9	93.7
Degraded	94.2	94.0	91.6	92.0	92.8	92.6	94.1	94.1
Accuracy	94.1%							
Kappa	Value 0.93							

2.10 Assessment of Historic Deforestation

Deforestation rates were estimated for the whole project area, for the following intervals: 1987–2001 (a period of 14 years) and 2013–2019 (a period of 10 years). The model used for calculating deforestation was according to Dirzo, 1990.

$$r = 1 - \{1 - [(A1 - A2) / A1]\}^{1/t} \times 100 \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

Where r is the deforestation rate, A1 is the area of forest at the beginning of the period, A2 is the area of forest at the end of the period, and t is the number of years for a given period (Dirzo, 1990). In this model, the rate of deforestation is expressed as the percentage of remaining forest that is cleared per year. From the three dates of land cover, the land cover changes were analyzed, specifically deforestation, by comparing land cover over time on a pixel by pixel basis. Deforestation was assessed at a number of different scales in order to understand how deforestation varies across the landscape

2.11 Determination of Deforestation Triggers

Interviews were conducted to determine the possible causal factors of deforestation.. Selection of persons to be interviewed was based on their roles in the community and members of the Mbe protection Eco guards. Simple percentage was used to rate the causal factors responsible for the deforestation as obtained from the interview sessions.

3.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Landsat imageries of Mbe Mountain and Wildlife Sanctuary (1987-2025)

Landsat imagery results of the study were presented for 1987, 2001, 2013 and 2019. Land cover maps were also projected for the period 2025 as shown in Figs. 3 to 7 and Tab. 3

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Fig. 3: Landsat imagery for 1987

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Fig. 4: Landsat imagery for 2001

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Fig. 5: Landsat imagery for 2013

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Fig. 6 : Landsat imagery for 2019

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Fig.7: Landsat imagery projected for 2025

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Table 3: Land Cover Statistics between 1987 and 2025

Land Cover Types	1987		2001		2013		2019		2025	
	Area (ha)	% Area								
Forest	6218.55	89.54	4941.18	71.15	4268.88	61.47	4106.07	59.12	3775.77	54.37
Degraded Forest	477.72	6.88	1271.52	18.31	2466.27	35.51	1983.78	28.56	2663.46	38.35
Non-Forest	248.94	3.58	732.51	10.55	210.06	3.02	855.36	12.32	505.98	7.29
TOTAL	6945.21	100	6945.21	100.00	6945.21	100.00	6945.21	100.00	6945.21	100.00

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Land use/cover (LULC) is an important component to understand the changes in the environment triggered by the interaction between human and the environment. Population increase in major cities has resulted in urban sprawl at an unprecedented rate, which according to Awuh *et al.* (2018) is projected to continue into the next era. The geometric increase in the global population has necessitated the building of services such as, settlements, to accommodate the growing population. These activities result in land conversion, such as, forest or plantations, agricultural lands and grasslands to grow impervious surfaces such as roads, sidewalks, parking lots, rooftops and bare lands (Wang *et al.*, 2015; Allegrini *et al.*, 2015).

According to Awuh and Amawa (2017), Aslan and Koc-San (2016), Enete *et al.*, (2014) and Brunsell (2006), land conversion to impervious surfaces is one of the main contributors to climate change and variability in different parts of the world which potentially affects the health of urban dwellers living in localities that continue to experience LULC changes. More also, land-use/land-cover change contributes significantly to earth-atmosphere interactions, forest fragmentation, and biodiversity loss and has become a major issue for environmental change monitoring and natural resource management (Wang *et al.*, 2015; Allegrini *et al.*, 2015). Therefore monitoring land cover dynamics in the urban area, in an appropriate and cost effective manner, is very important to local communities and decision makers. It enables the planning, management and conservation of natural resources and the environment.

In this study, land cover maps was used to evaluate change in land use system for the period 1987 – 2019 with a forecast for 2025. The land use system evaluated for the study were forest, degraded areas and Non forest areas. The term Non forest Areas refer to such surfaces as water bodies and rocky outcrops that were not visible from satellite imagery. The research findings were discussed under these land use systems.

3.2 Forested Areas

The results indicated a continuous decline in forest cover between the period 1987 – 2019 and by extension 2025. When the decline was subjected to statistical analyses, a p-value > 0.05 was obtained indicating a significant decline. Increase deforestation rates have severally been reported in literatures (Morgan *et al.*, 2019, Nicholas *et al.*, 2019 and Jeffery, 2018). This phenomenon is rated as the second gravest ecological problem after species loss (Cunha *et al.*, 2019). The deforestation rate was observed not to be uniform across the forest under study. This assertion observed in this study was also reported by Awuh *et al.* (2018). The rate was observed to be highest at Bamba, Bashu, Bokalum and Abo Mpong. The results also showed huge forest decline towards the areas bordering Okwango Division of the Cross River National Park. This findings is in conformity with that reported by Nchor *et al.*, 2018, Paul & Emeka 2015 in the Okwango Division of the CRNP. The call for the delineation of the CRNP boundaries which was also attributed to anthropogenic pressures further confirms the huge forest decline observed in this study. The possible triggers of deforestation in the area was obtained via interviews. The lack of basic understanding behind constraining the host community from accessing some parts of their forest encouraged poaching, hunting and farming activities. Negligent employment of these activities often result in frequent occurrences of wild fires. These triggers of wild fire have severally been reported in literatures (Ferrenberg *et al.*, 2019, Zhang and Lim 2019, Kong *et al.*, 2019 and Sun *et al.*, 2018).

Evaluation of forest cover between 1987 and 2013 (Figs. 3,4 and 5) showed a huge decline around Wula 1, Wula 11, Bamba, southern parts of Kanyang 1, Abo Ogbagante, Abo Mkpang and Abo-Obisu. The result returned Kanyang 1 as the only community with no forest decline during the 2013 period. Similar finding on these areas were reported by Enuoh and Ogogo 2018, and Shomkegh *et al.*, 2017. Interview session with the people of Kanyang 1 revealed the establishment of a Forest Offender Court administered by the ECO Guards. The research also established robust sensitization and awareness campaign program in the community. These conservation efforts were observed to be either nonexistent or ineffective during this period in the other communities with huge vegetal cover conversion.

Interpretation of the forest cover between 1987 and 2019 followed same trend as that evaluated for 2013. Interestingly, a fraction of the area observed as degraded in the 2013 imagery showed robust vegetal cover implying re-growths and cessation of disturbances. It was observed on interview that aggressive

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enlightenment campaign, enforcement of stiff penalties for encroachers complimented with aggressive tree planting campaign were embarked upon by the people of Kanyang 1 and 11.

If the disturbing trend in forest decline is allowed to continue as projected for 2025(Fig.7), there shall be no forest cover whatsoever in Bamba, Wula 1, Bamba, Kanyang 11, Abo Ogbagante, Abo Mkpang and Abo-obisu. It is also observed in the projection that intrusions of non-forest elements would permeate Kanyang 11 and some parts of Kanyang 1. The people made a strong case for official gazette of the forest either on its own or its incorporation into either Afi Mountain and Wildlife Sanctuary or the Okwango Division of the Cross River National Park as possible remedial measures.

3.3 Degraded forest

Evaluating 2001 imagery with that obtained for 1987 revealed about 12% conversion of forested areas into degraded landscape. The change was significant ($P < 0.05$) when statistically computed. Similar change in land cover maps was obtained by 1987 and 2025 in Mbe mountain protected area. Poaching, hunting and harvesting of timber and non-timber forest resources adduced as causal factors in those reports were similarly obtained during interview with community members in this study. All persons interviewed blamed the 2001 deforestation rate on lack of awareness, ineffective patrolling at Kanyang 1, nonexistence of ECO guards in other communities and weak enforcement structures.

The conversion to degraded forms continued to 2013 as shown in Fig 4. The increase in degraded area was observed to have arisen from zones not only previously occupied by forest but also for the first time, from non-forested components (water bodies and rocky outcrops). This assertion was arrived at when evaluation was made between the about 18% gain in degradation between 2001 and 2013 with the 10% loss in forest cover. This implied that 10% of the degraded areas in 2013 was derived from previously occupied forests while 8% were derived from either shrinking of water channels or mining of minerals contained in the rocky outcrops. This assertion was further confirmed on interview with community members who affirmed redirection of the stream to provide irrigation services to some large farms towards Kanyang 11, Abo Mkpang, Abo Ogbagante and Abo Obisu. The people do not confirm occurrence of artisanal mining in the area. The conversion of non-forested areas to degraded land forms observed in the 2013 imagery profile finds support in the reports of Yosio *et al*, 2019, Prevedello *et al*, 2019 and Shimamoto *et al*, 2018.

The imagery obtained in 2019 showed a less than 2% decline in forest cover. It also showed for the first time, a decline in degraded areas when compared to what was obtainable in 2013. This period of decline corresponded to the establishment of ECO guards in all the communities, sensitization campaign by Wildlife Conservation Society (WCS), increased funding and setting up of Offenders Court as enforcement measure. The strategy were more effective in Kanyang I and 11 communities as evidenced by reduction in deforested areas.

Regrettably, when projection was conducted for 2025 increase deforestation rate was obtained. Mkpang and Abo Obisu in 2025 and beyond. This is owed in part to non-sustenance of the effective conservation strategies currently in place as it was also revealed that current funding obtained by WCS for the area would elapse in 2021. If funding is thereafter not obtained and the trend festers, there may be no vegetal cover around Wula I Wula II, Bokalum and Abo Ogbagante in 2025 and beyond.

3.4 Non Forest Areas (NFAs)

Non forest areas as used in this study refers to such surfaces as water bodies, rocky outcrops and tour camps that were not large enough for quantification via satellite imagery. Similar constraint was reported by Awu *et al*, 2018.

NFAs were found exclusively around Wula, Kanyang 11 and Northern parts of Kanyang 1. This accounted for about 3% of the total land cover form as at 1987. However as at 2001, though size of area occupied by NFAs increased, it was observed that extent of occurrence decreases significantly around

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Kanyang 1 and 11 leaving fragments while previously forested areas in the southern axis around Abo Mkpang, Abo Ogbagante and Abo Obisu and the eastern flank around Bamba were converted to NFAs. During ground trotting, it was observed that some of the water bodies were permanent and others ephemeral (seasonal). It was also observed that channels for irrigation purposes were created which obstructed normal hydrologic flow regimes.

The size of NFAs in 2013 declined below its 1987 dimension. It was observed on interview that bush fallowing farming method often influences obstruction of water course to irrigate farm locations (usually outside the reserve) which frequently changes on yearly basis.

Water obstruction from the park for irrigation purposes was stopped in 2017 as a conservation effort. This action was complimented by the clearing up of blocked water courses in 2017 and 2018. This policy framework and action would have accounted for the increase in the NFAs in the 2019 imagery result as evident in Fig 4. The conservation efforts could have also influenced the increase in Extent of Occurrence (EOO) as revealed in NFAs presence in previously forested areas especially around the eastern flank bordering the Okwango Division of the CRNP. The evidential possibility in the cessation of funding for the Mbe reserve area was factored into the prediction modelling equation that returned a conversion of non-forested areas to degraded land forms in 2025.

In summary, Land use-Land cover maps produced for 1987, 2001, 2013, 2019 and a forecast for 2025 revealed some salient findings for the Mbe protected areas. First, there was general conversion from forested areas to degraded landscape in all the years under review except in 2019 where strict enforcement efforts halted the continual decline. Second, it was observed that degraded areas were derived from not only previously forested zones but also from areas previously occupied by water courses and rocky outcrops. Third, redirection of water channels and courses for irrigating farms outside the reserve was observed as a factor influencing changes in land use and cover. Fourth, continuous decline in forest cover and non-forested areas is predicted for 2025 with a corresponding increase in degraded areas. This may result in total loss of forest cover around Bamba, Abo Mkpang, Abo Ogbagante, Abo Obisu and Wula areas leaving Kanyang 1 and 11 only as zones occupied by forests. Therefore, there is an increasing need for the use of science based decisions for policy making in Mbe Mountain and wild life sanctuary which is critically important. This study has demonstrated the usefulness of landsat imagery in producing accurate land use/ land cover maps.

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